

Non-Invasive Assessment of Coronary Stenoses and Comparison to Invasive Techniques: a proof-of-concept study

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Abstract—Coronary Computed Tomography Angiography (CCTA) has gained substantial ground in everyday clinical practice due to its non-invasive nature. In this work we present a noninvasive method to assess the hemodynamic significance of coronary stenoses using only CCTA images. Two female patients were subjected to Invasive Coronary Angiography, Virtual Histology IVUS and CCTA. The same arterial segment was reconstructed in 3D using the proposed method as well as two already validated 3D reconstruction methods using the aforementioned invasive techniques. The lumen diameter reduction (%) and the minimum lumen diameter (mm) were calculated for all cases and a relative error <5% was observed between all three techniques.

Keywords—component; Coronary Computed Tomography Angiography; Stenosis; Noninvasive assessment

I. INTRODUCTION

Coronary artery disease (CAD) and especially atherosclerosis is the leading cause of death in the Western world. Atherosclerosis is a disease of the coronary, carotid, and other large arteries that involves a distinctive accumulation of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) and other lipid-bearing materials in the arterial wall [1]. Several risk factors, biological, genetic and environmental contribute to the occurrence and progression of atherosclerosis. Atherosclerosis tends to localize in regions with curvature and branches where blood flow deviates from its normal distribution patterns in straight vessels.

For these purposes, several invasive or noninvasive techniques have been developed that allow the visualization of the coronary vasculature in everyday clinical practice. Traditional Invasive Coronary Angiography (ICA), IntraVascular UltraSound (IVUS), Coronary Computed Tomography Angiography (CCTA) are some of the most well-known and used in everyday clinical practice. Every imaging modality has its pros and cons. For example, ICA

provides an accurate visualization of the arterial lumen but fails to deliver any information regarding the arterial wall or the presence of any atherosclerotic plaques. Moreover, in fully occluded vessels, due to the fact that the contrast agent cannot pass through the stenosed area, thus leaving the distal part of the artery invisible. IVUS on the other hand provides a 2D view of the interior of the arterial lumen, the arterial wall and a modest view of the atherosclerotic plaque. The cons of the aforementioned technique are that it does not provide information on the actual location of the examined frame, the rather inferior image quality as well as the artifacts that are created from strongly calcified plaques. Both methods are considered as invasive since they both require the use of a catheter. CCTA on the other hand is a noninvasive technique that gains ground in everyday clinical practice. It can safely provide data on the arterial lumen, the arterial wall and the atheromatic plaque. This technique also fails to deliver accurate information on the coronary vasculature when highly calcified plaques are present, the so-called “blooming effect”.

The progression of these imaging techniques has allowed the accurate 3D reconstruction of the coronary vasculature. Several attempts have been reported in the literature. IVUS-Angiography fusion methods [2], ICA derived methods [3] as well as CCTA methods [4] have been developed and are constantly gaining ground in the field of biomedical engineering. The ongoing advances in Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and their application on the 3D models that derive from the aforementioned reconstruction methods has constituted them a valuable tool for everyday clinical practice [5-12].

The purpose of this study was to improve the noninvasive assessment of coronary stenoses in comparison with invasive techniques, and to validate the method using several metrics such as the lumen diameter reduction percentage, the

minimum lumen diameter, the 3D centerline length, the mean WSS throughout the vessel and finally, the maximum WSS.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset

In this study, two female patients (mean age: 59 years) were recruited for ICA (Integrus Allurs Flat Detector), VH-IVUS (Visions® PV .018 Catheter, Volcano Corp.) and CCTA (Toshiba Aquilion 64-slice detector) exams at the InCor hospital of Sao Paulo. The Left Anterior Descending artery was used in both cases for our comparison. Anatomical landmarks were used to identify and reconstruct the same parts of the LAD.

B. 3D Reconstruction

a) VH-IVUS-Angiography fusion method

Both arterial segments were reconstructed following our already validated method [2]: the VH-IVUS frames were first binarized using an appropriate MATLAB algorithm and then the luminal and outer wall borders were automatically detected. Then, the luminal borders of each segment were segmented from the two angiographic views and the respective 2D centerlines were automatically extracted. The aforementioned 2D centerlines were then fused to create the final 3D centerline of the 3D model. The generated 3D centerline was used to stack the VH-IVUS segmented frames perpendicularly, thus creating the actual 3D arterial model. Using the annotated branches from the VH-IVUS images, the corresponding absolute orientation of the 3D model was performed, thus creating the final accurate 3D model of the arterial segment (Fig.1).

Fig. 1: Flow chart representing the reconstruction steps for the hybrid 3D reconstruction method. A) Lumen annotation in the corresponding VH-IVUS frame. B) 3D centerline extraction process. C) Final 3D model of the artery, back-projected on the corresponding angiography frame.

b) Quantitative Coronary Analysis

In order to display the arterial anatomy and to reconstruct the arterial segments we use a method based on coronary angiography [3].

The arterial segments were reconstructed using our in-house developed algorithm based on coronary angiography. The user manually segments the luminal borders of the artery of interest in the two angiographic projections, using specific landmarks that are visible in both views. Then, the algorithm automatically detects the centerline in each view and selects n equidistant points in each centerline. For each centerline, the perpendicular line in each of the n points is calculated and defined. In each projection the perpendicular lines intersect the luminal borders of the vessel projections in two points P_1^{Ang} , $P_1^{Ang'}$ having a distance r_1^{P1} and r_1^{P2} from the first and second silhouette, respectively. Then for each of the n points, n circular contours are computed with a radius that is calculated by:

$$r_1 = \frac{r_1^{P1} + r_1^{P2}}{2} \quad (1)$$

The whole reconstruction process is depicted in Fig.2. Finally, a 3D path is reconstructed using the same method as described before (a. VH-IVUS-Angiography fusion method) and the circular contours are stacked perpendicularly on the 3D centerline, thus generating the 3D arterial model.

Fig. 2: 3D reconstruction procedure with our 3D-QCA method [3].

c) Coronary Computed Tomography Angiography

Another validated method to quantify CAD is CCTA. We utilized our 3D reconstruction method [4] according to the following steps:

- i. For the automated definition of the region of interest (ROI), we used the Frangi Vesselness filter on the pre-processed CCTA images (Fig.3-A,B).
- ii. Removal of the blooming effect, which is generated from highly calcified plaques.
- iii. Extraction of the 3D centerline.
- iv. Estimation of the weight function for lumen, outer wall and calcified plaque is made with using Hounsfield Units (HU) values and the distance from the centerline. Finally, an active contour model is applied for the lumen and outer wall.

- v. A level set algorithm is applied on plaque segmentation considering calcified objects of significant size.
- vi. Final 3D reconstructed models for lumen, outer wall and calcified plaques are generated (Fig.3-C).

Fig. 4: CCTA 3D reconstruction process. A) Initial CCTA frame. B) CCTA image after the application of the Frangi-Vesselness filter. C) Final 3D model of the artery of interest. Transparent green: Outer Wall, Brown: Lumen, White: Calcified Plaque.

C. . Blood Flow simulations

In order to examine the efficacy of the CCTA reconstruction method, we performed the same blood flow simulation on each method. The flow simulation parameters are described below in detail.

a) Rigid Wall assumption

The Navier-Stokes and the continuity equations were used to model blood flow:

$$\rho \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \rho(\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} - \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} = 0, \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) = 0, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{v} is the blood velocity vector and $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the stress tensor, which is defined as:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = -p\boldsymbol{\delta}_{ij} + 2\mu\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij}, \quad (4)$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta, μ is the blood dynamic viscosity, p is the blood pressure and ε_{ij} is the strain tensor calculated as:

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla \mathbf{v} + \nabla \mathbf{v}^T). \quad (5)$$

Blood was considered to be Newtonian with dynamic viscosity 0.0035 Pa·s and density 1050 kg/m³. The generated flow was considered laminar and incompressible. The Reynolds number ranged from 508-730.

b) Boundary Conditions

At the inlet a flow velocity of 0.15 m/s was used in all cases. At the outlet, a zero pressure boundary condition was used, whereas for the wall, a no-slip and no-penetration boundary condition was used.

c) Mesh

Fig. 3: Final 3D models of the LAD of patient 1. Light yellow: CCTA method, Blue: VH-Angio method, Dark yellow: 3D QCA method.

The final 3D models (Fig.4) were discretized into tetrahedral elements with an element face size ranging between 0.09-0.1 mm. Five layers of brick elements from the interface to the core of the artery were created. The element size was determined after a mesh sensitivity analysis. The maximum number of iterations for the convergence of the solution was set as 60 and the convergence criterion was set to 10⁻⁴.

III. RESULTS

Our primary goal in this study was to examine and investigate the efficacy of a non-invasive method of coronary stenosis severity assessment compared to two validated invasive techniques. This was done by calculating the lumen diameter reduction (LDR %) in all three 3D models for each case. In order to calculate the aforementioned percentage, we used the ratio of the diseased part of the artery (area with the smallest lumen diameter) to the healthy one. Moreover, since the same landmarks were used for all three 3D reconstruction methods, we also calculated the 3D centerline length. Furthermore, in order to investigate the effect of the reconstruction method on the computational fluid dynamics simulations, we calculated the mean WSS as well as the maximum WSS for each case.

Table 1 depicts the calculated lumen diameter reduction percentages, as well as the minimum lumen diameter (MLD) values, the 3D centerline length, the mean WSS and the maximum WSS.

TABLE I. CALCULATED LUMEN DIAMETER REDUCTION, MINIMUM LUMEN DIAMETERS, CENTERLINE LENGTHS, MEAN WSS AND MAX WSS FOR ALL CASES

Patient #	Metric	VH-Angio	CCTA	QCA
1	LDR (%)	52	50	53
	MLD (mm)	1.17	1.34	1.75
	Length (mm)	56	60.2	56.3
	Mean WSS (Pa)	4.1	4.2	3.7
	Max WSS (Pa)	51	53	44
2	LDR (%)	36	30	34
	MLD (mm)	2.8	2.9	3.1
	Length (mm)	71.2	73.8	71.7
	Mean WSS (Pa)	3.4	3.5	3.1
	Max WSS (Pa)	31	34	24

IV. DISCUSSION

In this work, we examined the efficacy of our in-house developed CCTA 3D reconstruction algorithm in the assessment of the severity of coronary stenoses. In order to achieve that, we compared the exact same coronary segments to the ones deriving from two already validated in-house developed 3D reconstruction methods deriving either from the fusion of VH-IVUS-Angiography images or from ICA images. The results were very promising, since the relative error in both examined cases was <5%. Regarding the length of the 3D centerline of each model, the VH-Angio and the 3D-QCA methods exhibited merely equal results since they share the same algorithm regarding the 3D centerline extraction. The CCTA method exhibited slightly higher length values with a mean difference of 4.9%. Regarding the mean WSS values, the 3D-QCA method exhibited the lowest values, mainly because the 3D models were smoother than the other two methods. However, the average WSS as well as the maximum WSS values generated by the other two methods were directly comparable, thus indicating that the non-invasive method produces accurate 3D models of the coronary vasculature. In spite of the modest dataset that we used, the preliminary results indicate the accuracy of the examined method and may potentially replace the traditional invasive coronary imaging techniques. We are expanding our current dataset in order to further validate and establish the proposed method.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Our study demonstrated the efficacy of a noninvasive technique in the assessment of the hemodynamic severity of a coronary stenosis. However, several cases must be added to the existing dataset in order to establish the validity and accuracy of the proposed method.

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